

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D5.1 FIRST DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION, EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN 30/06/2023

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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FIRST VERSION

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Abstract	D5.1 introduces the CATALISI Plan for dissemination, communication, exploitation and sustainability, which is a comprehensive and living document that outlines the tools, channels and activities to be put in place throughout the project to ensure successful and consistent visual representation of the CATALISI project, as well as its activities for successful dissemination of results.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.1 presents the CATALISI Plan for Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability, which outlines the tools and channels that will be used throughout the project. More precisely, the presented set of rules and standards within the document will govern CATALISI partners through effective communication with target audiences from the starting point of the project. It will also map out the activities to be done throughout the CATALISI project in light of the focus areas of this deliverable and interconnection of this Work Package (WP) and other WPs.

The Dissemination and Communication plan includes a clear distinction between dissemination and communication activities, with dissemination focusing on public disclosure of project results, and communication consisting of strategic measures to promote project activities to a wider audience. The exploitation plan of this project consists of getting to a stage in which the knowledge generated on the project might be exploited at a large scale by the project participants themselves or might be attractive to other entities outside the consortium.

This deliverable will act as a living document which means that strategies and channels will be revised and updated to align the best with challenges at any given time and adapt to needs of both implementers and target audiences. The next and final iteration of this deliverable is due at M36 and it will encompass all of the changes made in the meantime and present conclusions in terms of communication, dissemination, exploitation and sustainability.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CoP	Community of Practice
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DCO	Dissemination and Communication Objectives
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
LL	Living Labs
KER	Key Exploitable Results
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1. PROJECT INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND AIM

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the EU have been recognized for their global leadership in the fields of Research and Innovation (R&I). In order to maximize research impact and institutional transformation, HEIs need to strengthen their European University collaborations.

By bridging the gap between HEIs disparities in terms of R&I performance, HEIs can navigate and cooperate in the production and dissemination of high-quality knowledge to maximize the value of research and its impact within the European Union.

CATALISI model focuses on three main domains (Human Capital, Research Modus Operandi and Finance) intersected by seven acceleration services (Living Labs, Design Lab for transformational pathway, Counselling, Capacity Building and Outreach, Predictive Studies on Skills Anticipation, Community of Practice, and Marketplace), which are designed to facilitate and catalyse the process of institutional transformation.

The aim of CATALISI is to help and support Higher Education Institutions to successfully implement strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services.

These are designed to facilitate and accelerate institutional transformations in the field of R&I which will strengthen European Universities collaborations and alliances as lighthouses of European values.

1.2. STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable consists of the following sections:

- **Chapter 1:** The first chapter provides a brief introduction to the CATALISI project and the main objectives of this deliverable.
- **Chapter 2:** This chapter introduces the main objectives of Dissemination and Communication activities, as well as the methodology and approach used in designing the Dissemination and Communication Plan.
- **Chapter 3:** The third chapter offers an overview of the Dissemination Strategy and presents the expected outputs to be disseminated and the engagement strategy.
- **Chapter 4:** In this chapter, the Communication strategy is presented with a detailed description of the project's visual identity and the channels and tools to be used. It also details networking and liaison activities with other initiatives.
- **Chapter 5:** This chapter addresses Exploitation and Sustainability. It outlines the activities that will be taken throughout the project in order to guarantee that the project outcomes are exploited both during and after its lifetime.
- **Chapter 6:** This chapter reflects on the importance of this document and upcoming activities.
- **Appendix:** Presenting Dissemination, Communication master sheet.

The strategy and plan of dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement will be continually monitored, updated, and reported during the project, with the next version of this deliverable being released at M36.

1.3. METHODS

The Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan is executed through close interaction among all consortium members to create a multiplier effect on identified and engaged relevant stakeholders. Moreover, to expand the reach of the CATALISI findings it is of great importance to perform Dissemination and Communication (DC) activities in accordance with the principles of simplicity and consistency.

These principles apply to the project outlook, materials, as well as interactions tailored to the project's target audience - at the right time - in the right environment. For the project strategies to work, it is essential to understand the profile and features of the targeted stakeholders in the first place, including the implementers - partners in the project that act as first use-cases. Having in mind the specific community that universities, as implementers are, and the wider audience that project needs to engage (from academia, business, public administration and civil society), project channels, language and messages must be adequate and adapted in terms of easy understanding between different groups.

When it comes to exploitation, the plan of this project consists of getting to a stage in which the knowledge generated by the project might be exploited at a large scale by the project participants. First step is to list all exploitable assets identified at the beginning of the project. As the project advances and a more tailored approach can be developed, CATALISI consortium partners, especially implementers, will be assessing their individual current state, goals, and steps to successfully exploit any results generated by the project or by themselves. As the last step, a general exploitation plan, as well as the individual ones are going to be honed and put in the context of sustainability - use and impact even after the project lifetime.

1.4. SYNERGIES WITH OTHER TASKS AND DELIVERABLES

Deliverable D5.1, as well as the entire WP5, is cross-connected with all work packages and all partners participating in CATALISI. Therefore, important content and findings made in other WPs are to be used and relied upon to update the strategies in this document and draft the final version.

Concretely, it is important to underline the connections to:

- WP1 - Acting-LL co-creation. This WP will conduct a stakeholder mapping for each of the acting LLs (Living Labs), identifying key actors along the complete value chain, outlining their responsibilities and influences, mapping them into a 4-helix model. It will also facilitate knowledge exchange among different LLs, including the potential for replicability.
- WP2 - Knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme. Learning Hub and Twinning activities under this WP are of particular importance for the Dissemination and Communication activities, and in long term for sustainability as well.
- WP3 - Design, Coaching and Sustainability. Coaching and mentoring as well as studies for the implementation of transformational pathways and marketplace developed within this WP will provide significant input for both exploitation and sustainability. Dissemination and communication activities will rely on the outputs of these services and knowledge for extending the reach.
- WP4 - Evaluation and Impact Assessment. Relevant aspects of this WP to this deliverable and its next iteration are focused on the state of the affairs and impact measurement of the implementation of various services by implementers. Another important task is Development of monitoring and impact assessment toolkits used to understand whether the desired change occurred and whether the goals were reached.

- WP6 - Project Management. This Deliverable is written in accordance with internal procedures set by the project coordinating team.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

2.1. OBJECTIVES OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The dissemination and communication (DC) efforts of CATALISI are closely linked to the project objectives and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The DC plan is designed to uphold the project objectives and KPIs by promoting the CATALISI project, the contributions of its partners and stakeholders, and its accomplishments. This is done to engage a broad audience and attract potential future partners who are relevant to the project's exploitation goals. The specific objectives for dissemination and communication (DCO) are outlined in [Table 1](#).

TABLE 1: DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

DCO1	Raise awareness among the key sectors dealt by the project on the role of CATALISI and its social innovation framework, societal, economic and knowledge impacts;
DCO2	Ensure decision-makers are informed about the project, inciting policy related uptake and spill over;
DCO3	Foster synergies with other initiatives, capitalising on existing dissemination channels and networks to ensure efficient communication and understanding of the CATALISI transformational pathways, use cases and best practices;
DCO4	Introduce new patterns of conduct in the target groups and end-users of the project results and build wider networks of early adopters
DCO5	Support the exploitation strategy by attracting potential investors and/or financial backers for the post-project market deployment, as well as to develop collaborations with SMEs and startups.

The above DCO have been established to influence behaviour and to raise awareness among specific target groups. These objectives address five key questions: **Why** (the purpose of the DC action), **What** (the message/content to be disseminated and communicated), **To whom** (the target audience), **How** (the method of dissemination and communication), and **When** (the timing of the DC activities).

Dissemination and communication activities are integral and encompassing, often occurring simultaneously, and targeting various existing and potential audiences throughout the project's duration. However, it is important to note that these activities should extend beyond the project's lifespan. The practical experience and guidance generated by the project will hold relevance for stakeholders both within the European Commission (EC) and beyond EU Member States as the academic domain has a very strong influence on other academic systems in Europe.

Establishing clear dissemination and communication channels among project partners and engaging a wider community will be pivotal to the project's success. These channels will

facilitate effective information exchange and collaboration, fostering lasting impact beyond the project itself.

2.2.CATALISI TARGET AUDIENCE

2.2.1. Target groups and key messages

The first step toward developing a strong DC strategy is a deep understanding of the CATALISI target audience and tailoring both dissemination and communication activities to the specific needs of each target group. Each target group has its own sphere of communication, and our aim is to address our target audience in a more meaningful way. Understanding each target audience allows us to address them with effective content through the appropriate communication and dissemination channels, and with more relatable, non-generalised content.

Target audience for CATALISI was pinpointed already in the proposal stage as following:

- **TA1: Policy Makers:** policymakers at local, regional, national, European, and international level with interest in and influence on institutional transformations
- **TA2: Higher Education Institutions and Alliances:** universities across Europe
- **TA3: Civil Society:** Associations, groups of interest and more in general people with strong interest in institutional transformations in the Higher Education Sector.
- **TA4: Local and Regional Governments**
- **TA5: Researchers and Research Organizations**
- **TA6: Funding Organizations:** European Commissions, national Ministries of Research and Innovation, Banks, public and private foundations, and local national and international level that can finance initiatives on institutional transformations.

These CATALISI stakeholders are key players relevant for institutional transformations of HEIs, belonging to the quadruple-helix ecosystem (public authorities, industry, academia in different sectors, and civil society), including funding organisations. With the goal of understanding them in a more meaningful and human-centric manner, we will develop joint activities and discussions, and share experience to build collective knowledge in their shared domain of interest. It is important to underline that the above target groups are multilayered and can be understood as audiences of different relevance and level on involvement in the project.

CATALISI's external target audience will be involved in expertise knowledge sharing and knowledge access, learning opportunities, networking, visibility, and recognition, by contributing to the project activities and outputs, and influence and impact, where they can provide feedback, insights, and recommendations on the project activities and outputs. Among this external audience there is a Community of Practice (CoP), a group of people who share common interests, valuable and different expertise, and experience in institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions.

Therefore, based on the initially drafted target audiences, they could further be placed in broader groups, based on the level of involvement in the project to: **general audience**, **external audience directly related to the project** and most direct - **audience directly in connection to the project**. Depending on their level of involvement they key messages reflect the depth of information that will be conveyed to these groups.

General audience: All target audiences (T1-T6) in a broader sense and not directly involved or benefiting from the project but interested in the project outcomes.

External audience directly related to the project: TA2, TA5

Audience in connection with the project: all target audiences, however on an expert level and as direct participants in the project through quadruple helix approach that will be used in CATALISI workshops.

TABLE 2: CATALISI TARGET AUDIENCE, KEY MESSAGES & CHANNELS

Target Group	Key Messages (WHAT)	Tools and Channels (HOW)
General audience (GA)	<p>Institutional transformation starts with getting all relevant stakeholders onboard;</p> <p>Current challenges CATALISI is aiming to tackle</p>	<p>Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, media pack (for journalists)</p>
External audience directly related to the project (EA)	<p>3 domains in which CATALISI will be working on;</p> <p>7 implementers acting as use cases;</p> <p>Ways to join to project - Community of Practice;</p> <p>Predictive studies</p>	<p>Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, events, media presence of CATALISI partners</p>
Audience in connection with the project (PA)	<p>Predictive study and tools</p> <p>Environmental, social, political, and technological changes that are dictated by market trends and universities' challenges and pathways based on our use cases.</p>	<p>Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, events, scientific publications</p>

The list of the target audiences will be reviewed during the project's progress under dissemination activities by all the partners. This will be done also through the process of stakeholder mapping performed by several CATALISI partners and led by ENOLL.

The focus of the stakeholder mapping will be on identifying key actors along the complete value chain, outlining their responsibilities and influences, mapping them into a quadruple helix model (actors representing academia, business sector, public administration and civil society). Throughout the project, this activity will go in depth by accessing not only the key actors but also local context, barriers and framework conditions that can influence the institutional transformation. This will be done in several iterations through surveys, workshops, and in-depth interviews.

2.3. MONITORING OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

To achieve the successful implementation of Dissemination and Communication activities, and fulfilment of the relevant objectives and KPIs as presented in Table 9, a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation.

The impact of the CATALISI communication activities will be monitored on an ongoing basis and reported in the final deliverable: D5.2 Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plan. Nonetheless, the monitoring takes place throughout the entire project so that it is possible to adjust any strategy or approach to these activities as needed.

The monitoring system will provide evidence on whether the CATALISI Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) is being implemented as initially planned and scheduled.

It will also address potential implementation problems and determine whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. An example of the table intended for gathering data on Dissemination and Communication activities is showcased in the Appendix I of this Deliverable.

Below are the DC KPIs, showcased with concrete activities and target groups that will benefit from different outputs of the project. In addition to the CATALISI target groups already mentioned, CATALISI implementer (project partners) have been added as well in order to underline which are the outputs they will mostly use or benefit from.

TABLE 3: CATALISI DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION KPI TABLE

	Diss/ Comm	Timing	Outreach/ KPI	Target Group
Brand Identity: Logo & Templates It will comprise brand guidelines, colours and font codes, and the logo variants needed for all applicable online or offline channels and collaterals	D/C	M2-M36	1 brand identity kit	All groups
Dissemination Events: The consortium will co-organize with projects under the same topic and other related projects (even national) a workshop	D	M1-M36	3 workshops	HEI institutions and alliances, universities, researchers; CoP members; Quadruple helix stakeholders
Webinar series: webinars with project partners to present outcomes of the case studies which will be available online and on YouTube	D	M1-M36	At least 5 webinars	CATALISI implementers
Meetings and exhibitions: bilateral meetings, international conferences and relevant exhibitions and trade fairs	D	M1-M36	5 bilateral meetings, 2 international conferences, 2 exhibitions	HEI institutions and alliances, universities, researchers; Quadruple helix stakeholders; Funding organizations both public and private; General public

Toolkits, contents and recommendations: Exploitable assets will include a package for project results dissemination	D	M1-M36	1 policy brief, 1 scientific poster, Factsheets and reports per request	CATALISI implementers,
Communication materials package: preparation of a set of communication material comprising the project logo and visual identity	C	M6 (first version), M24 (second)	1 project brochure, 1 roll-up banner, 2 posters and flyers	All target groups
CATALISI website: will be the primary contact point for those external to the project, and it will communicate key information about the project.	D/C	M4-M36 and beyond	1 website, 30.000 visits from 27+ countries	All target groups
Promotional videos: short videos presenting the project	C	M1-M36	1 promotional video, 2 video teasers for social media campaign, 10+ promo banners, 10 thematic CATALISI cards	All target groups
Online communication: A series of interviews and feature articles featuring each test cases' products published on the project website, distributed on EC communication channels and to selected media. Also shared via e-newsletter.	C	M1-M36	2 newsletters/year	All target groups
Media Relations: social media networks and a YouTube channel will be used to host videos and audio-visual material.	C	M1-M36	3 social media accounts	All target groups

In addition to the above-mentioned, to assess the quality of communication and dissemination, the project uses the following methods:

- **Press coverage:** Partners will provide feedback on local press coverage, or any coverage made by their own outreach, to assess the impact of communication and dissemination efforts and gauge the correlation between the messages conveyed and public perceptions. The outcome will reveal the areas of interest, which can be leveraged to generate more similar stories or identify the need for strategic adjustments.
- **Feedback:** Partners document the input received from events and new contacts established, and they report any emerging opportunities resulting from these activities. Feedback obtained helps evaluate the outcome's quality, identify new or validate existing stakeholder needs, measure the impact, and determine whether the strategy is effective or requires revision.
- **Website:** The website will utilize the Google Analytics system, which includes a built-in statistical feature. This feature will provide valuable data on various metrics such as the number of live viewers, the number of archived views, the geographical locations of viewers, and the duration of their visits. This data will be instrumental in evaluating the effectiveness of the website's content and its overall online presence.

Communication and dissemination efforts will be classified according to the level of impact: communicate to build an understanding of the goals and the benefits, communicate to build a deeper understanding of the benefits, and communicate for action.

2.4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PROCEDURE FOR INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PROJECT EVENTS

Each partner's participation in (e.g. external conferences, workshops etc.) and/or organisation of project events must be reported to the WP5 leader in a timely and regular manner, so that their involvement can be followed up with well-designed dissemination and communication activities. If dissemination activities include any project results protected through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), review and approval of the CATALISI coordinator and consortium representatives will be required. Additionally, as stated in the GA:

“The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests. A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.”¹

The DC procedure has been set up to:

- I. Produce high-quality CATALISI publications and presentations
- II. Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information.
- III. Monitor and record the dissemination activities of the project appropriately.

Table 4 presents a step-by-step detailed plan for events execution that every partner must follow.

TABLE 4: PLAN FOR EVENTS PARTICIPATION AND ORGANISATION

Planning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communicate with WP5 leader (F6S) to align with the event organiser ideally one month in advance ● Share event concept (including event title, goals and objectives, draft agenda/programme, target audience, date and time, format (online/onsite) and location, key stakeholders involved, if is a local/national or international level, expected number of participants, any other information) ● Prepare registration forms: Ensure you adhere to GDPR and data protection in relation to sharing attended contact details and consent to recording events and sharing photos of participants

¹ Article 17

- If needed, secure event suppliers (e.g., photographer/videographer, catering)
- If applicable, prepare printed materials for distribution: make sure any communication material you produce, publish and share about the event includes the project logo, EC emblem and disclaimer
- If applicable, look for possible partnerships with SMEs and private actors, as well as HEI alliances

Prepare social media templates and content to use during the event (F6S responsibility).

Promotion

- Share with F6S the news in English if you want to promote your event via project website and other project tools
- Announce the event on the website (F6S)
- Produce social media and blog content (F6S alongside the partners involved in the event)
- Spread the message through all partners, channels and stakeholders (F6S)
- Make pre-event information available for attendees (F6S alongside the partners involved in the event)

If applicable, write and send an event Press Release (F6S alongside the partners involved in the event)²

During the Event

Applicable to in-person project organised events

- Test Wi-Fi connection
- Attendance list: Always collect the signature of participants attending your online, face to face or hybrid event. The signature list must include the title of the meeting/event, date and place, project title, project logo and EU emblem + disclaimer
- Make sure there are indications for all locations
- Ensure that all attendees and/or speakers have an updated schedule
- Keep information updated: posts on social media using diverse visuals, such as photos, videos and live streams
- Go over the social media and project channels in the intro session and encourage newsletter's subscription

Applicable to online events

- Test Wi-Fi connection
- Ensure that all attendees and/or speakers have an updated schedule

Keep information updated: posts on social media using diverse visuals, such as photos, videos and live streams.

Post-Event

- **Report** the activity via email to F6S (APRE in cc) and in the Dissemination and & Communication master sheet³.
- Analyse what worked and where improvements can be made. **Event feedback** form: If you plan to share a feedback form with the participants, remember to include the privacy statement.
- Create at least one blog post about the event⁴
- Share event photos: make sure you have explicit consent from participants
- **Dissemination and communication:** promote the outcome of your event via the project channels. Share with F6S (cc APRE) the News item including a visual if you want to promote your event via project website and other project channels.
- If applicable, publicly thank all attendees for their participation.

Post-event engagement with publication of event outcomes on social media channels and potential follow-up events.

³ Appendix I

⁴ F6S will edit the final version of the text to be published to provide a coherent narrative by the project team including the tone of the voice in reporting. Also, final editing will include potential rearrangement of the text in terms of Search Optimization Engine requirements.

2.5. PARTNERS ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

All partners will be engaging in general communication and dissemination activities. This is both at the consortium level and as part of Work Package activities and areas of their respective expertise. Partners will work together in mapping out and organising relevant activities and participate in events of special importance to the development of the project, cooperating with target audiences, as well as other connected projects and initiatives.

Partners are encouraged to integrate dissemination and communication actions into all CATALISI activities. Especially in the case of CATALISI implementers, bringing forward best practices and details of their experiences as use-cases will be valid to create synergies with other partners and channels, as well as a wider audience. Partners are also encouraged to welcome local and national media (press, radio, TV), offering interviews, visits and demonstrations.

Moreover, as set out in the GA, partners are obliged to communicate and disseminate the project and its results making them available to targeted and general public. Specific provisions for dissemination (dissemination restrictions) are set out in the GA (Grant Agreement) and the CA (Consortium Agreement).

All deliverables marked as public will be made available for preview and download on the CATALISI website after they have been reviewed and approved by the consortium and the European Commission (or clearly marked as pending approval, if applicable). Dissemination and Communication of results from deliverables classified as sensitive need to be approved by the consortium (see section) or any partner that produced and/or is affected by the publication of such results. The partners' responsibilities regarding communication activities have been defined as follows:

1. All partners have efforts dedicated to communication and dissemination activities, through the channels and tools described in this document.
2. The dissemination lead (F6S) will support partners in the implementation of the dissemination and communication activities.
3. All partners are responsible for providing content related to their project activities to enable the creation of blog posts on the project website, as well as content to be used throughout different CATALISI channels.
4. The development of the project newsletters is a responsibility of F6S, and all partners provide information and content related to their project activities.
5. The management of the social media networks is a responsibility of F6S.
6. All partners are responsible for actively interacting with the project social media networks.
7. All partners are responsible for regularly and timely reporting their communication activities.

3. CATALISI DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The primary objective of the dissemination activities is to share the knowledge and results generated within the project, enabling others to utilize and benefit from them. By doing so, the impact of the project funded by the European Union is maximised.

According to the guidelines outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), it is mandatory for the partners to disseminate the project's results by making them publicly accessible, unless specified otherwise (such as in cases involving intellectual property protection, security regulations, or legitimate interests). Specific guidelines regarding dissemination, including any restrictions, are provided in both the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement

(CA). While executing the dissemination activities, according to the mentioned agreements, the partners are committed to respect the following obligations.

Open Access to Scientific Publication

Requirements for beneficiaries are to ensure open access to their peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to project results. These requirements include depositing a copy of the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a trusted repository for scientific publications, providing immediate open access to the deposited publication, and providing information about any research output or tools necessary to validate the publication's conclusions. The metadata of deposited publications must also be openly available (more details about open meta data are provided in CATALISI Data Management and Quality Plan. Only publication fees for fully open access venues are eligible for reimbursement. Beneficiaries must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to meet open access requirements.

As mentioned above, the listed target groups could be broken down into more specific ones, depending on the level of their involvement. Therefore, for the more specific target audiences of the dissemination the CATALISI Dissemination Strategy is focused on i) the external audience directly related to the project results and ii) the audience in connection to the project. On the other hand, considering the defined level of the dissemination, the strategy is focused on dissemination for understanding and dissemination for action. Dissemination for awareness is focussed on general audience and overlaps the most with the Communication activities.

TABLE 5: CATALISI STAKEHOLDER GROUPS AND EXPECTED IMPACTS OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Level	Target	Targeted Audience Profiles (to WHOM)	Expected Impacts (WHY)
Dissemination for Awareness	General audience (GA)	<p>General Public: European citizens & stakeholders at large.</p> <p>Civil Society (citizens and CSOs) interested in the project outcomes, Higher Education Institutions and Alliances, Regulation community, policy makers, European Commission, National governments, National decision-makers, Associations, related initiatives.</p>	<p>Awareness about the project, objectives, results and impact;</p> <p>Increased awareness for the need of institutional transformation and better connection to industry and market;</p> <p>Creation of an ecosystem based on quadruple helix.</p>
Dissemination for Understanding/Uptake	External audience directly related to the project results (EA)	<p>Research & academia stakeholders: EU associations, partnerships, Universities, PhDs and students, research institutions, technological centres, experts.</p>	<p>Enhance and stimulate further research and innovation activities between project partners;</p> <p>Create media interest to get their involvement and support;</p> <p>Stimulate and support further research.</p>

Dissemination for Action	Audience in connection with the project (PA)	<p>End-users (Universities, companies, local innovation ecosystems and policy makers on local, national and EU level)</p> <p>Funding Organizations: European Commissions, national Ministries of Research and Innovation, Banks, public and private foundations.</p>	<p>A strong brand image;</p> <p>Stimulation of the ecosystem consisting of academia, civil society, business representatives as well as policy makers towards use of CATALISI outputs, creation of guidelines and tools on finance initiatives and support for further projects and activities in the domain of institutional transformations.</p> <p>Providing use cases for 3 CATALISI domains that could be replicated/scaled.</p>
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Finally, the focus of the dissemination activities in respect to the timeline of the project are presented in the [Table 6](#) below.

TABLE 6: DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES PHASES

Dissemination Activities	
Phase	Focus
Phase I (M1-M18)	Approach-oriented content: dissemination of workshops’ outcomes, call to join the Community of Practice ecosystem, promotion of the Living Labs, promotion of mobilization and mutual learning (MML) workshops and the Catalyst (marketplace)
Phase II (M18-M48)	Result-oriented content: project intermediate and final results. Dissemination of the results and achievements.
Post-project period	Result-oriented content: project final results. Dissemination of the results and achievements.

3.1. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

CATALISI will leverage the strong positioning of its partners, including their involvement in initiatives, platforms, academic and entrepreneurial ecosystems, active participation in conferences and events, experience of regular publication of scientific content, among other strategies. These efforts aim to reach and influence different target groups. Each partner will concentrate on engaging specific target groups. F6S is leading Work Package 5, providing support and coordination while utilizing its extensive industrial network to amplify the impact of the project results and heavily relying on the input from other work packages (as indicated in Chapter 1.4).

All partners are required to plan their dissemination activities, and they will report on their accomplishments regularly, following the timeline of their planned activities.

The primary project dissemination activities are detailed in the following subchapters.

3.1.1. Scientific Conferences and Events

CATALISI partners will actively engage in international and local conferences/meetings, whether held virtually or in person, beyond the scope of the project itself. This participation serves to disseminate the project's results and create awareness about the activities and accomplishments of CATALISI.

Each partner will provide regular reports on their involvement in conferences and events related to CATALISI, whether they are attending or hosting such gatherings. The anticipated activities and events in which partners are expected to participate include:

- Scientific Conferences, dissemination events, exhibitions, and collaborative events with other H2020/HORIZON EU projects at both national and international level.
- Workshops, courses, seminars, and training sessions.

Through active involvement in these diverse activities, CATALISI aims to reach a wider audience and facilitate the sharing of project outcomes while fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange within the research community. Below is the table showcasing external events different CATALISI partners will attend and present the CATALISI methodology and outcomes until the end of 2023. This table acts as a living document, which all partners update on a regular basis to plan annual events attended.

TABLE 7: CATALISI PARTNERS' EVENTS CALENDAR

Name of the event	Date and place (online, hybrid, live)	Partner
International Action Research Summer Camp Action Research Conference Austria	June 11 to 18, 2023, Innsbruck, Austria, in person	UCC
Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice, Final Conference	June 14-15 th , 2023, Castelló de la Plana, Spain, in person	UJI
QS Higher Education Summit	June 27-30 th , 2023, Dublin, Ireland in person	UCC
EUA EGOS group meeting	June 29 th , 2023, Brussels, Belgium, in person	KTU
IASIA international conference ""The Futures of Government and Governance in a VUCA World: Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous"	July 31 - August 4, 2023, Manila, Philippines, in person	KTU
Higher Education Institutional Research Network Conference	September 7-8 th , 2023, Kingston upon Thames, UK	UCC
ENOLL OpenLivingLab Days 2023	September 21-23 rd , 2023, Barcelona, Spain, in person	AUTH, UCC and ENoLL (organizer)
European Service Learning Conference	September 25 to 27 th , Rome, in person	UCC
ECIU University Research Conference	October 3-4 th , 2023, Barcelona, Spain, in person	KTU
UCC Community Week	October 23-27 th , 2023, Cork, Ireland , in person	UCC

3.1.2. Project Organised Events

For the entire duration of CATALISI, different internal activities to the project will take place in order to provide assessment on the current challenges implementers are facing, to include stakeholders from quadruple helix and to disseminate CATALISI outputs and solutions to wider audience. For that purpose, each HEI will undergo a set of workshops as part of the Living Lab methodology (WP1) - one workshop per HEIs including the respective quadruple helix stakeholders in the first round which is already taking place at the time of writing this deliverable, followed by second iteration from M9 onwards.

As part of the collaboration with sister projects and relevant initiatives, events will be organized for the purpose of showcasing CATALISI results and how they could be implemented by stakeholders and other projects.

In addition, under the lead of APRE, stakeholders belonging to quadruple helix and acting as experts in their respective domains are invited to join CATALISI Community of Practice (CoP). In this regard, a separate series of workshops and events will be organized. The knowledge sharing events are organized to connect different HEIs around Europe and other societal actors to share their knowledge, best practices, and expertise in placing the research results into practical use.

CATALISI Learning Hub will serve as a platform to support and document the workshops, trainings and other material relevant to both CATALISI partners and external stakeholders, whereas the Catalyst (marketplace) will also contain funding opportunities (including events) organized both by consortium and externally.

4. CATALISI COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The CATALISI communication plan consists of proactive and well-planned communication efforts, with tailored messaging - both in terms of type of content and in the way the content is communicated with an aim of connecting with general as well as specific key players and their engagement among research innovation ecosystems; fostering networking, experience sharing and boosting the dissemination and exploitation of CATALISI's most relevant outputs.

In order to demonstrate the impact and advantages of participating in CATALISI, the communication strategy follows a funnel approach. This approach enables active engagement, effectively communicates the project's outcomes, and uses various communication channels and activities to reach different groups within the target audience, starting from the target audiences of CATALISI to a wider one that has interest in the project but was not initially engaged in it. For recognizability of the project, a consistent approach is adopted by the entire consortium to synchronise communication efforts. This implies visual identity that is uniformly used across different project materials, the use of suitable media and formats, as well as tailored messages to engage with the project target audience.

This is particularly important as there are 7 implementers in CATALISI, each with their own set of specific needs and outputs. Valuable knowledge and content for communication will be gathered from project deliverables, partner interactions, case studies, partner publications, and other interactions with target audiences. This knowledge will then be shared through CATALISI communication networks to promote the achievements of the project.

4.1. CHANNELS AND TOOLS

CATALISI will develop and use key communication tools and channels, including online, offline, and interactive (face-to-face) methods. All these channels and tools will be implemented by the CATALISI partners to establish efficient and effective interactions with key stakeholders. While certain content will have a general focus, other posts, articles and other communication materials will be tailored to specific target groups.

Having in mind the expertise and diverse engagement of CATALISI partners with their respective audiences, the project will prioritise the use of distinctive communication channels that have proven successful in their day-to-day interactions with different audiences.

4.1.1. Visual Identity

An integrated and cohesive visual identity serves as the foundation for all communication products and tools, establishing a strong brand for CATALISI. The visual branding, including the project logo and style, will ensure that external audiences can easily recognize CATALISI and contribute to raising awareness of the project by presenting a unified identity right from the project's start. All dissemination and communication tools, such as the project website, Twitter account, and LinkedIn page, as well as presentations, posters, roll-ups, documents, etc., will adhere to the visual identity developed for the project. This guarantees a professional and consistent appearance across all deliverables, internal as well as external presentation of the project and its outputs.

4.1.2. Logo

The development of a visual identity and a project logo ensures that project outputs are consistent and easily recognisable. CATALISI logo was presented and chosen during the project Kick off meeting. The choice was made by the entire consortium based on the associations that project keywords invoke. Along with the logo, a brandbook, clear logo concept and colour palette were presented and later made available to all partners. The CATALISI Logo is presented in its two versions in [Figure 1](#).

FIGURE 1: CATALISI LOGO

4.1.3. Colour Palette

In addition to the logo, colour is the first visual clue which represents the project. Colours presented on the logo as well as on the Figure below are deeply connected to the keywords that we associate with the project, namely: education, transformation, training, policy and acceleration. Next to the sleek design of the logo, blue as the main colour is used as a sign of stability and reliability. Moreover, blue is often used by businesses and initiatives that want to project an image of security as well as to inspire creativity and productivity. CATALISI colours are showcased below:

FIGURE 2: CATALISI COLOUR PALETTE

4.1.4. EU Funding Acknowledgement

Across all outputs of the CATALISI project, and accompanying the logo, a text concerning the source of the project’s funding will be provided along with the European flag, as shown in Figure below:

FIGURE 3: EU FUNDING ACKNOWLEDGMENT

In addition, any dissemination of results must indicate the following:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

In the case of CATALISI, the granting authority is the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

4.1.5. Document Templates

CATALISI consortium partners are provided with a Word Deliverable Template as well as PowerPoint template. This is important to ensure the standardisation of the project documentation. Also, it contributes to coherent representation of visual identity throughout the project lifetime. The templates are made available through the internal repository system established by APRE as coordinator. Additional presentations, templates and other materials will be designed by the Communication Manager. All partners should use the CATALISI PowerPoint template when presenting the project and/or its outcomes both at internal and external events. Template examples are presented in the figures below.

FIGURE 4: CATALISI DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

FIGURE 5: CATALISI PPT TEMPLATE

4.1.6. Visuals and Graphics

In addition to the word and ppt templates, several templates and visuals were prepared in order to present the project on social media channels. Based on the project visual identity, the templates are adapted to social networks as needed. Mandatory element is the project logo, present in every template to maintain coherence throughout all communication efforts.

Coherent representation of the project is crucial for its recognition. The logic behind this approach is like with any other brand, the visual identity can be tailored but must always remain recognizable and with clear connection to the project.

FIGURE 6: CATALISI SOCIAL MEDIA VISUALS - EXAMPLES

4.1.7. Online Presence

CATALISI Website

Nowadays, the internet serves as the ultimate platform for communication and interaction, particularly when it comes to reaching broader or specific target audiences across different geographical regions. The CATALISI website <https://catalisi.eu/> was launched in M3. However, it is envisioned as a dynamic platform that will continuously evolve and expand throughout the project. This website serves as the primary interface for engaging with the public and community of practice, and effectively caters to the diverse target audiences of CATALISI. It provides essential information about the project, its events, and how individuals can participate or support the project,

The CATALISI website plays a crucial role as a management tool, significantly enhancing the communication and dissemination of project activities and outcomes to a wide range of stakeholders at all levels. Moreover, it serves as an accessible resource for the general public and local citizens.

F6S regularly updates the project website by incorporating contributions from all partners. The website showcases details regarding the project's objectives, partners as well as the scope of CATALISI in its initial phase and the acceleration services it will provide. This online platform will also include testimonials, working materials and activities, downloadable promotional materials, deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, and videos.

Additionally, it serves as the gateway to the “CATALYST” (name as agreed amongst consortium members, initially called CATALISI Marketplace) and the CATALISI Learning Hub.

FIGURE 7: CATALISI LANDING PAGE

The Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions have also been incorporated into the CATALISI website, outlining the general rules and policies governing visitors' usage of the website.

The website provides direct access to social networks through clickable icons located in the footer conveniently after the main text on each page. This allows users to easily participate when visiting the website. To ensure efficient updates and changes to the CATALISI website, the consortium follows the instructions detailed below:

- Updates and changes requested via email: A description of the required integration or change should be provided as an attached .docx file, rather than in the text of the email request.
- If the integration or change involves documents or files to be uploaded on the public website, they should be attached to the email.
- The description should clearly specify the type of integration or change requested, including the specific part(s) of the website that need to be modified. Links to the webpage(s) requiring upgrades should be provided.
- The use of abbreviations should be minimised. If used, abbreviations must be explained explicitly, at least when initially mentioned in the description of the requested integration or change.
- Events to be included in the News section should be sent with all the necessary details (date, title, location, program, and link) to ensure consistent levels of information and content.

Considering the nature and progression of activities throughout the project's lifespan, as well as related information, the CATALISI website will be continuously updated and enriched with relevant content.

Partners' websites

CATALISI Partners will use their own websites to promote the general awareness of the project. Since 4 partners are facilitators and 7 implementers (universities), each partner will play a role in their own network of stakeholders when communicating about the project and disseminating its results through their own internal channels (i.e., mailing lists, newsletters, social medias etc.). In addition to the websites, the same applies to partners' social media and tailoring the effort in the outreach according to where their target groups are mostly present.

4.1.8. Social Media Channels Mix

To expand the reach of the CATALISI project and foster two-way communication, active participation in social media channels will be encouraged. The selection of social media channels for CATALISI focuses on platforms that project partners have successfully utilised to engage with their customers and stakeholders, ensuring maximum usability and impact.

Regular posts will be shared to facilitate the flow of news and continuous content updates. While some partners will reserve their social media channels for special occasions, CATALISI leverages various social media platforms to enhance visibility, accelerate knowledge sharing, promote project outcomes, and engage with the public, particularly stakeholders connected to the work of CATALISI implementers. By regularly providing updates on their work and other activities within the project, we aim not only to share insight but have onboard external stakeholders - within the Community of Practice and other means of participation in the project.

In addition, all of the CATALISI partners will actively participate in the outreach to relevant media outlets. It is worth noticing that in the case of universities, each of them have an established procedure for communication as well as the communication office and long term collaborations through which they inform the public about their projects.

In the table below, a list of media outlets is listed to which the outreach for CATALISI can be made. Again, in order to be able to expand this list, it presents a living document that partners will update accordingly.

TABLE 8: MEDIA OUTLETS

Media outlets	
Leggo	https://www.leggo.it/
Metro	https://metronews.it/
Il Messagero	https://www.ilmessaggero.it/
La Repubblica	https://www.repubblica.it
Science Guide	https://www.scienceguide.nl/
El Periódico Mediterraneo	https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/
Castellón Información	https://www.castelloninformacion.com/
Castellón Plaza	https://castellonplaza.com/
Delfi	https://www.delfi.lt/en/
15min	https://www.15min.lt/
Mokslo Lietuva	http://mokslolietuva.lt/
technologijos.lt	http://technologijos.lt/
lrytas.lt	https://www.lrytas.lt/
tv3.lt	https://www.tv3.lt/

Kas Vyksta Kaunas	https://kaunas.kasyksta.lt/
VORIA	https://www.voria.gr/
Typosthess	https://www.typosthes.gr/
ERT news	https://www.ertnews.gr/
Iatronet	https://www.iatronet.gr/
CNN Greece	https://www.cnn.gr/

CATALISI has established a presence on two social media channels: a LinkedIn page and a Twitter account (links available below). Instead of broadening its efforts to more platforms, the choice of the two platforms was made having in mind the overall goals of the project. In the context of communication, this goal is more specific - to reach professionals, policy makers, business representatives as well as academics on LinkedIn as a professional network, but also provide opportunity for more informal tone through updates on Twitter, which is more likely to reach deeper into each of these communities on a personal, and not only on professional level. Research has been conducted to identify relevant hashtags, some of which are already being utilised. In case of CATALISI, they are: #catalisi (to create a specific project-related hashtag), #acceleration, #highereducation, #institutionaltransformation. In addition to these hashtags which are sufficiently narrow or on the contrary wide, we aim to capture the attention of both a very specific audience as well as the wider one that could take interest in our topics. This is particularly important to reach the stakeholders which are traditionally entirely tied to academia and their ecosystem such as business owners.

On the 16th of June 2023 (M6), the overview of CATALISI's social media total followers is the following:

TABLE 9: PRESENT SOCIAL MEDIA STATUS

Social Network	Followers
LINKEDIN	254
TWITTER	30

4.1.8.1. Content Types

The purpose of our content marketing efforts is to showcase the project progress, work done as well as its outputs. In addition, we aim to attract and onboard relevant stakeholders to CATALISI Community of Practice (CoP) as well as to showcase the advantages of using CATALISI marketplace (the CATALYST) and Learning Hub. For these purposes, different types of content will be developed, as described in the table below.

TABLE 10: CATALISI TYPES OF CONTENT

Attract	Engage	Maintain	Involve
Content about the project scope, methodology, objectives and services, partners' presentations, partners' testimonials.	Blog posts, articles, success stories, events news, interviews and showcase of results and key findings.	Email marketing, social ads and retargeting initiatives as well as continuous knowledge sharing and expansion of services on Learning Hub and CATALYST	Events, workshops, conferences, etc.

FIGURE 8: EXAMPLES OF CATALISI SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS (LINKEDIN AND TWITTER)

4.1.8.2. LinkedIn Page

The LinkedIn project page⁵ is leveraged for targeting content at all the stakeholders of the quadruple helix, especially academia and business stakeholders. The advantage of LinkedIn as the biggest professional network is precisely the presence of different stakeholders which can then be involved in one joint ecosystem. From CATALISI perspective, it is a place open to all who are interested in learning about the project, its opportunities, services, knowledge sharing, searching for events, funding or best practices and getting more involved with the project.

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/catalisi-project>

Frequency of posts: once to twice per week throughout the project, depending on the phase of the project, increasing in frequency during phases such as events and results sharing. LinkedIn will be sustained by content created by F6S and content provided by the partners.

FIGURE 9: CATALISI LINKEDIN PAGE - SCREENSHOT

4.1.8.3. Twitter page

Despite the major shift in the nature of Twitter in terms of trustworthiness and control of data, at the time being, it remains a channel with the possibility of wide reach to the stakeholders, which is essential for the project's success. Partners involved in the project have the chance to publish and engage even with a more personal tone on this platform and create a connection to target audiences different than those more engaged on LinkedIn. The community will be formed around various activities (mostly workshops) that will take place for both CATALISI implementers and externally (as in the case of CoP). CATALISI Twitter profile⁶ is an important addition in the toolkit for communication and dissemination.

Frequency of posts: from one to three times per week throughout the project, increasing in frequency during critical phases, such as events and results sharing. Twitter will be sustained by content created by F6S and also content provided by the partners.

⁶ <https://twitter.com/catalisproject>

FIGURE 10: CATALISI TWITTER PROFILE - SCREENSHOT

4.1.8.4. Other channels

Besides the listed channels, CATALISI will also communicate with audiences through email (compliant with GDPR treatment of personal data), webinars, and newsletters, by distributing important news, sending press releases, and through partners' channels. CATALISI consortium Partners will target relevant online newsrooms with articles and contributions as well as offer interviews.

Relevant EC and other channels such as newsrooms and blogs will be targeted, and collaborations with other projects (and their channels) will be leveraged. In order to support the upcoming activities in the project, a CATALISI YouTube channel⁷ and a Zenodo channel⁸ were created, and a project page will be created on the F6S platform to foster research and development strategies that can be targeted in a business context.

4.1.9. Newsletter

The CATALISI project will develop and distribute an online newsletter to highlight important project milestones, notable events, and activities. It will also feature updates from the field and other relevant projects when applicable. The newsletter aims to ensure the involvement of all CATALISI partners.

The newsletters will be released approximately every six months (bi-annually) and will be designed to be clean, informative, and with clear calls to action. Our goal is to maximize the reach of the newsletter and achieve a high opening rate while keeping the bouncing rate low.

Visitors to the project's website will have the option to subscribe to the newsletter, as a subscription button displayed in the website footer. Additionally, recipients have the option to unsubscribe at any time using the link provided in each issue of the newsletter. All collected data will be stored and saved in compliance with GDPR regulations and will not be accessible to third parties.

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAyIQwhSMDmOldoQD0lDsJA>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/catalisiproject/>

In order to ensure active engagement and onboarding of new stakeholders, CATALISI will consider the following strategies:

- **Responsive email design:** We will utilize the Mailchimp platform, a real-time email marketing automation tool, to design and distribute responsive and targeted email campaigns. This approach will provide an enhanced reading experience for recipients and enable comprehensive reporting and analytics.
- **Dynamic customization and personalization:** The email opt-in form on the CATALISI website will only require the user's name and email address, simplifying the subscription process while still allowing for customization and personalization.

By implementing these measures, CATALISI aims to maintain a strong connection with its audience and deliver valuable and tailored content through the newsletter.

Never miss our newsletter

I consent to receive the Catalisi Newsletter.

You can unsubscribe at any time by clicking the link in the footer of our emails.
By subscribing, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn about Mailchimp's privacy practices.](#)

FIGURE 11: CATALISI NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION FORM - SCREENSHOT

The newsletters will be sent by email to subscribers and shared on CATALISI social networks. There will also be a dedicated part on the website for the newsletters, where they can be accessed at any time. In order to achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, CATALISI partners will be encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their network of contacts.

4.1.10. Promotional Material

Media Communication and Press Releases

CATALISI project will generate press releases and other material to disseminate relevant news, with a focus on regional, national, and European electronic media. Targeted platforms and journals may include those tackling the topics around academia, research in general as well as the ones in relation to educational reforms. Partners will be requested to distribute the press releases within their regions/countries and share them with their professional networks. The first press release has already been published.

All press releases will be accessible on the CATALISI project website and shared through social media channels. Whenever applicable, the information about the project will be written in the national language of the partners, in layman's terms, unless appropriate to the publishing channel. This approach aims to ensure that the respective audience can easily comprehend the project's objectives and the benefits it offers.

Printed Materials

CATALISI project will develop a range of promotional materials, with a preference for digital formats to minimize environmental impact. Partners will be encouraged to share these materials during suitable occasions, ensuring that CATALISI reaches the intended target audience.

Communication materials relevant to events, such as postcards, stickers, folders, notebooks, and t-shirts, may be produced upon request and in advance. These materials will be distributed at relevant events. Such examples are factsheets, posters and other ad-hoc materials as shown in the figures below.

FIGURE 12: EXAMPLE OF AN EVENT POSTER

FIGURE 13: CATALISI COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE FACTSHEET

Poster and roll-up banner stands are designed for display at CATALISI-hosted events and external events relevant to the project. Partners will be responsible for printing these materials and other necessary materials locally, following recommended layout and design suggestions to ensure consistency.

FIGURE 14: CATALISI POSTER

4.2.NETWORKING AND LIAISON WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

The project partners will share the project activities and by engaging in networking and informal meetings. Whenever possible, official presentations by CATALISI will be utilised to showcase the project's achievements and progress at various stages of its development.

In addition to promoting the project and its outcomes on the above-mentioned channels, for better uptake of the project best practices and other findings, CATALISI will establish strong connections with other pertinent initiatives funded by the European Union, international organisations, or national programs, thereby increasing awareness and impact on the target audience. The partners will also explore opportunities to participate in each other's events and jointly organise activities. To facilitate these collaborations, both centralised and decentralised linkages will be established at different levels of the project.

Potential collaborations with sister projects funded under the same call (namely aUPaEU project coordinated by Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya and the Accelerate_FutureHEI project coordinated by University Industry Innovation Network BV) have been identified. These are related to the establishment of joint initiatives such as development of joint policy briefs, collaboration around evaluation activities, participation as members of the CoP as experts, participation in the CATALISI external evaluation board and mutual event/workshops organisation and participation.

4.3. POLICY IMPACT COMMUNICATION

Activities focused on policy impact play a crucial role in encouraging the dissemination of acquired knowledge and best practices. To achieve this, guidelines for actions will be shared, and policy recommendations will be developed based on the impacts of these actions on

institutional transformations. WP4 will serve as a source of strategic information and guidance, offering policy recommendations regarding the structural and institutional changes necessary to enhance the value of research and its impact within the European region. Tools and channels that have been setup within the Dissemination and Communication Plan will facilitate partners in reaching the policy relevant audience and communicating policy relevant outputs and activities within the CATALISI Project.

EY will develop policy recommendations for universities, university alliances, general policy makers at local, national, and European level. Strategic information about the structural and institutional changes that are needed to maximize the value of research will be provided as well as its impact within the European region.

Two policy briefs are also foreseen as project deliverables: D6.2 at the end of M12 and D6.3 at the end of the project (M36) and will be led by APRE, in alignment with UCC (as WP4 leader) and EY. These documents present research and recommendations to a non-specialized audience and serve as a vehicle for providing evidence-based policy advice to help readers make informed decisions.

5. EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

The primary aim of the exploitation efforts is to maximize the adoption of CATALISI's results beyond the project's duration. Developing an effective exploitation strategy is a flexible process that must be customized to suit the project's needs and the partners involved.

In order to facilitate this process, CATALISI facilitators will organize workshops and training, impact assessment as well as assessment on which exploitation paths are best suited for each partner so the exploitation strategy and plan can be collaboratively developed with the partners. These workshops will foster transparency and enable partners to gain a better understanding of each other's expectations.

In summary, the CATALISI Exploitation Plan will aim to enhance and expedite the wider uptake of some project outputs. This will be achieved by developing an exploitation strategy for each output and providing support to the partners involved in carrying out further exploitation activities at different stages of the project.

5.1 METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS FOR PROJECT EXPLOITATION

First step is conducting a comprehensive analysis and assessment of the current situation in the Intervention Areas of the implementers. These areas were identified during the proposal preparation phase as potential targets for institutional transformation. The assessments will be conducted for each Higher Education Institution (HEI) involved in the project, evaluating their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis), as well as their available resources. This analysis will shape the current and future operations and strategic goals of the HEIs.

The primary goal of SWOT analysis is to increase awareness of the factors that go into making a business decision or establishing a business strategy. To do this, SWOT analysis the internal and external environment and the factors that can impact the viability of a decision:

TABLE 10: SWOT ANALYSIS AND ASSESSMENT

SWOT	(Helpful to achieving the objective)	(Harmful to achieving the objective)
Internal origin (attributes of the organisation)	Strengths	Weaknesses
	Identify characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others	Identify characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others
External origin (attributes of the environment)	Opportunities	Treats
	Identify elements in the environment that the business or project could exploit to its advantage	Identify elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the business or project

The predictive study (T3.3) that will be led by EY serves as a basis for comparing the different states of affairs among the HEIs and more specifically, it is related to the demand of professional skills. In this initial exploration phase, the needs and perceptions of the HEIs are also considered to ensure better alignment throughout the subsequent phases.

The Explore assessments are carried out through qualitative in-depth interviews (assessing the state of affairs of the intervention areas of implementers), surveys and co-creative workshops led by ENoLL. They are co-designed and co-implemented by both the facilitators and implementers. The information gathered from these surveys will be used to develop an evaluation framework for the post-assessment, which will be conducted after the completion of the acceleration services and Research and Innovation (R&I) activities. After the Explore phase, CATALISI partners will be able to draft their first Individual Exploitation plans.

Therefore, In the first stage, all results with potential for commercialisation will be identified, and such potential will be evaluated, confirming or discarding their exploitation potential. In the second stage, action plans for the results selected will be designed. The third stage will develop exploitation plans defining the specific actions to execute such action plans.

In parallel to the exploration phase of the project, the identification of the Key Exploitable Results (KER) takes place, based on the KERs identified already at the proposal stage, updated and revised as needed.

When engaging in exploitation activities, these are the key objectives that should be followed by all partners:

- Establish and maintain mechanisms for effective exploitation and coordinate all levels and types of exploitation of the knowledge produced by the project.
- Inform stakeholders and targeted user communities where a two-way interaction will take place with the project development and encourage interactions/networking.
- Ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means.
- Channel the project’s results to a truly wide international audience, in particular in those areas where the proposed solutions will lead to immediate society impacts.

5.2. KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KER)

The CATALISI Exploitation Plan will use the KERs to identify and quantify the most effective exploitation activities that provide benefits and solutions, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education in higher educational institutions.

KERs will be expanded during the implementation of the project to ensure that all potential outcomes are addressed. Each approach will be carefully designed, tailored to the target audience and assessed to maximize the impact of the project.

Key exploitable asset types considered in CATALISI are:

- Scientific discovery, model, theory
- Services (new or improved)
- Business model (new or improved)
- Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
- Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy
- Event (conference, seminar, workshop)
- Learning and training (learning modules, curricula)
- New or improved infrastructures or facilities

TABLE 11: LIST OF KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

KER Name	Description	WP
CATALISI Marketplace (The Catalyst)	Online Single Entry Point showcasing different services offered by CATALISI partners and different learning opportunities, such as matchmaking events with SMEs, learning hub, coaching and funding opportunities	WP3
Living Labs	This service aims at guiding and mentoring implementers on co-creation methodologies and competencies in line with the Living Lab (LL) methodology. This will enable the institutional transformation of HEIs (acting-LLs) into user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings	WP1
Counselling service	stakeholders will benefit from counselling service which aims at empowering and supporting universities by providing guidance and best practice examples.	Transversal
Learning Hub	Training programmes to support the implementation of actions leading to institutional transformation. All webinars will be recorded and published on the project website. The Learning hub will be based on a virtual platform - which will also be open to the broader society	WP2
Policy Briefing	Policy feedback on the acceleration services, and widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups to promote Reform and Enhance the EU R&I system and increase trust in science and R&I outcomes, also fostering a two-way communication between science and society.	WP4 and WP6

5.3. INITIAL BUSINESS MODELLING

The objective of the business modelling activities in CATALISI is to derive a set of business cases and plan to support sustainable research and opportunities of the CATALISI offerings in eventual commercial operation. For this to happen, commercial exploitation of the CATALISI offerings and individual components is foreseen, upon which additional commercial features can be developed. The main objective is to facilitate the acceptance of CATALISI and a strong uptake and utilisation by HEIs, SMEs and stakeholders of the results, platform and marketplace.

Concrete plans will be finally presented in D5.2 due M36. Nevertheless, it is relevant to mention that CATALISI will focus on four different business cases, namely:

1. CATALISI Marketplace for research commercialization and innovation
2. Living Labs for open innovation ecosystems
3. Counselling services for empowering and supporting universities
4. Learning hub for the implementation of actions leading to institutional transformation.

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) will be used to visualise elements of the project. The BMC visualises a business structure in a simple way, but it also allows experiment with the modification of the blocks and one can estimate trade-offs. The BMC used in CATALISI is showcased below:

TABLE 12: BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationships	Customer Segments
Key partners' Resources offered within the project	Activities that our value propositions require. Distribution Channels Customer relationships Revenue streams	Value delivered to the customer Products and services offered Customer needs	Relationship across Customer Segments Integration in the business model	Most important customers Niche Market
	Key Resources		Channels	
	Key Resources our value propositions require Distribution Channels Customer Relationships Revenue Streams		Channels used across different customer segments Integration between channels	
Cost structure		Revenue Streams		
Costs inherent in the business model related to key activities and resources		Value our customers are willing to pay Revenue Stream contribution to overall revenues		

5.4. LEGACY AND IP RIGHTS

As a general rule, CATALISI will follow the provisions of Horizon Europe on knowledge management and protection, as set out in the Grant Agreement (GA) and developed in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

The key IPR-related issues to be considered in collaboration with APRE are ownership and protection of knowledge and access rights; management of the partners' background; and management of the IP results jointly developed by several partners within the project. Optimal IPR protection options (e.g., patent, utility model, copyright, trademark, confidentiality), will be proposed in line with the business model options and considering possible co-ownership. More in depth on data management will be provided in D6.1 - Data and Quality Management Plan.

5.5. EXPLOITATION MONITORING

CATALISI exploitation strategy aims to guarantee that the project outcomes are exploited during and after its lifetime. Therefore, this strategy needs to be adapted to the different stages of the project and take into account that as the project develops and the results are delivered, there will be a higher focus on results and exploitation activities.

Furthermore, the final iteration of the plan, D5.2 (M36) will provide more detailed information about CATALISI exploitation strategy and the actions that will be implemented during and after the project's lifetime. Table below provides an overview of the next steps/actions that will be implemented during the next couple of months.

TABLE 13: NEXT STEPS ON CATALISI'S EXPLOITATION PLAN

Action	Description
Internal discussion of the exploitation and sustainability strategy	During the project lifetime, project partners will discuss internally CATALISI exploitation strategy. In addition, sessions dedicated to exploitation will take place in CATALISI consortium meetings so that the final exploitation takes into account inputs from all the project partners. F6S (as WP5 Leader) will support/guide the internal discussions about exploitation and will collect all the inputs from the discussions.
Definition of further KPIs	CATALISI will discuss the KPIs defined in the proposal to successfully measure the effectiveness of the exploitation of the project results. The KPIs will be discussed internally during the Consortium Meetings and presented in D5.2 due M36.
Enlargement of the exploitation actions	The enlargement of the exploitation actions will be discussed internally during the Consortium Meetings and presented in D5.2.
Use of dissemination and communication tools	Dissemination and communication tools (especially the project website, newsletters, and social media) will be continuously used to disseminate CATALISI results and outcomes.

CATALISI's activities are and will be monitored, evaluated, and continuously updated as part of the ongoing quality control and management. The objective of the performance monitoring of exploitation is to guarantee that the project achieves the aims defined in the exploitation plan.

6. CONCLUSION

This deliverable (D5.1) introduces the CATALISI dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, a comprehensive and living document, which outlines the tools, channels and activities to be put in place throughout the project to ensure wide acceptance and sustainability of the CATALISI Project.

This document outlines the strategy, activities and tools with which the CATALISI Project will communicate with a range of stakeholders as well as the timing of the various activities throughout the lifetime of the project. The Consortium recommends a periodic review of this document to ensure it includes up-to-date contents and opportunities for disseminating and communicating project information.

In the upcoming months, partners will continue working in the identification and further elaboration of the Key Exploitable Results, strategic business plan linked to each KER and the final IPR generated during the project. Once expected results from the partners are identified, results of each partner can be addressed in order to elaborate an individual exploitation plan.

7. APPENDIX I

Type of activity	Activity name	Type of dissemination or communication activity (What)	Target Audience (Who)	FOR DISSEMINATION ONLY: Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 words) - (Why)	FOR COMMUNICATION ONLY: Communication channel (How)
Communication	Publication of	Others	TG2 Higher Education Institutions and Alliances. TG3 Civil societ		Newsletter
Dissemination Ac	Training for WII	Dissemination event (training)	WIDERA NCPs	To incentivize dissemination of practices to other target groups. The WIDERA NCI	

FOR COMMUNICATION ONLY: Outcome. Insert Key Performance Indicators	Status	Partner responsible	Partners that participated	External participants that need to be emphasized	Date	Website/URL	Materials from the event, MAKE YOUR OWN FOLDER in this format: YYYY-MM-DD-name of the event here: https://bit.ly/41kzDaN
E-newsletters. 1475 members re	Delivered	APRE	APRE	Access to acad	3-Apr-23		
Project 'WIDERA.NET' (https://	Delivered	APRE	APRE	WIDERA NCP	30 may 2023	https://horizons3DF_7OseDN2YA?e=5C655B	https://apre.sharepoint.com/f/s/catalisi2/E/w72skHqnJGr6t3YB-5_yYBs-cQnuj5-3DF_7OseDN2YA?e=5C655B

FIGURE 15: CATALISI DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MASTERSHEET